

A Study on Agriculture Finance and Agriculture Insurance in Microfinance

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Abstract

Agriculture finance and agricultural insurance are strategically important for eradicating extreme poverty and boosting share prosperity. Globally, there be situated an estimated 500 million small holder agriculture households representing 2.5 billion people- relying to varying degrees, on agricultural production for the livelihoods. The benefit of our work include the following: growing don't come off farmers and agricultural SMEs through commercialisation and access to better technologies, increasing resilience through climate smart productions, risk diversification and access to financial tools and smoothing the transition of non-commercial farmers out of agriculture and facilitating the consolidation of farms, assets and production (financing structural changes)

Keymessages

- Agriculture finance authorizes poor farmers to rise there wealth and food production to be able to nourish 9 billion individuals by 2050.
- Our graft in agriculture finance aids clients provide market-based security nets, and supply long-term investment to funding sustainable economic growth.
- Demand for food will escalation by 70% by 2050; minimum \$80 billion annual savings will be desirable to meet this demand.

There is an ever accumulative need to invest in agriculture due to a extreme rise in global population and varying dietary predilections of the upward middle class in evolving markets towards extraordinary value of agricultural Products. In addition, climate risk increases the need for investments to make agricultural more resilient to such risks. Approximationssuggest that ultimatum for food will rise by 70% by 2050 also at least \$80 billion annual reserves will be required to meet this demand, most of which requirements to come from private sector. Financial sector institutions in developing countries learned a disproportionately lower share of their loan portfolios to agriculture compared to agricultural sector's shares of GDP.

On the other side, the development and deepening of agriculture finance market is forced by a variety of elements which include

- Inadequate policies.
- High transaction cost
- Covariance of production, market and price risks
- Absence of adequate instruments to manage risks.
- Low levels of demand due to disintegration and in embryonic development of value chain

What we do

We focus on developing and implementing agriculture finance Strategies and instruments to crowd- in private sector,enhancing access to suitable financial services to farmers- particularly smallholders- and agricultural small and medium enterprises (SMEs) as a way to growth agricultural output and income, and simplifying their consolidation/ assimilation of production and promotion entities in agriculture to attain Economics of scale and stronger occurrence in the markets.

We primary work on agriculture finance, agriculture insurance and its linkages with agriculture finance.Our key areas of work are described below-

- Policies and regulatory interventions agricultural finance:We conduct diagnostic studies on the state of Agricultural finance within client countries and produced concrete action plans to Reform public policies and regulations in order to create an allowing environment to assemble agricultural finance.Some examples of policy and legal or regulatory intervention areas include lending quotas, interest rate caps,bank branch expansion regulations, Prudential regulation impacting agricultural lending, warehouse receipts financing frameworks, and alternative dispute mechanisms for contract farming.
- Policy (and insurance product development) advisory agricultural insurance:we advise government on policies for agriculture insurance (example financial incentives, premium subsidies, and the overall role of government to promote agricultural insurance) and on development of effective insurance products. Furthermore, we also work in partnership with the Global index insurance facility (GIIF) and the disaster risk finance and insurance program (DRFIP) on definite projects and activities.
- Strengthening of relevant Institutions: we provide technical assistance to reform and build capacity of public Financial Institutions, to establish commodity exchanges, and to build capacitive of MIFs and other Institutions.We operate a special program focused on financial co-operatives, given the importance of these entities as providers of financial services to smallholder farmers, rural MSMEs and household.This program aims to strengthen the performance as well as to enhance applicable regulations and oversight arrangements to better integrate them into their country's financial system.Furthermore, we design and implement in projects risk sharing mechanism through various instruments, such as partial risk guarantees.
- Knowledge management and community of practice:Informed by our in house Research and knowledge production, we carry out activities both at the internal level (including community of practices and training programs) and at the external level (Global and regional dissemination events, - South exchange and capacity building for policy reforms, among others) we organised to community of practice one on agriculture finance and insurance and another one specific to financial cooperative.
- Global engagements:Since 2011, we have served as a technical advisor to the G20 Global partnership for financial inclusion (GPMI) SME finance subdivision on issues related to Agricultural money and insurance.Also, we have moulded a partnership with Rabobank on financial organisations that aims to subsidize to the Global knowledge on this Foundations and the elevation building on concrete skills.

Financial Inclusion and Microfinance

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About 90% of the 180 million poor families in the region lack admittance to institutional financial facilities. Most formal Financial Organisations deny the poor their service area because of professed high risk, the high cost elaborate in small transactions, and the poor inability to provide vendible Collateral for loans. Persuasive financial inclusion is a common growth theme for most emerging countries in Asia and the Pacific then is key to comprehensive and composed economic growth as long as the poor with enhanced facilities to save in addition to have improved access to recognition and insurance benefits them to manage risk, built assets, contains income, and enjoy better life.

Digital Financial Services

Offering basic financial services through mobile phone auction devices, and networks of slight scale agents, digital financial services (Dfs) refrain the potential to blowout more people, at a lesser cost, then with greater suitability than traditional “brick plus mortar banking services”.

With the Fast global expansion of technology, mobile banking & other E- financial services are helping massive number of previously excepted people access financial services. cellular network operatives, administrations & Financial Institutions, spreading from large commercial banks to microfinance organisations, identify and have instigated to force the potential of DFs a figure of government and there Central banks take also embarked on “cash –lite” plans to reduce the use therefore cost of cash in their economies.

Dfs models are actuality tested with varying degrees of achievement around the world. Safaricom’s m-pesa in Kenya is perhaps the best known in addition most prosperous example of mobile banking. Its success Spark a upsurge of start-ups and enterprises that use the services to provide ravines other valuable services, such as service payments, savings accounts and also micro insurance.

Researchers are studying attainments and failures of ordinal financial services to recognise the market forces, commercial models and eco system necessities to support effective Dfs developments some where else around the world.

Mongolia Finance Sector fact Sheet

This fact sheet provides concise information on Mongolia finance sector and summary of ADB- assisted programs, contests and future directions.

The Asian Development Bank (ADB) as a extensive history of secondary Mongolian’s finance sector. The first rendezvous was in 1991, just after Mongolia joint ADB, when advice and volume building was providing to the Mongolian stock exchange aimed at its operations. Since then ADP as maintained Mongolia finance sector complete \$130 million in lending programs, \$109 million in mechanical assistance (M A) projects, and \$98 million dollars in secluded sector Investments.

Mongolia finance sector, despite several improvements, is still very fragile. The Economist heavy Reliance on the mining sector exposes the finance sector tourist from global price fluctuations in commodities. Risks have been rising and the finance sector currently suffers from high level of nonperforming loans. This is inhibiting banks from making original loans needed for economic recovery.

Many improvements have been made in terms of the capacity and the range of financial products and public services, and the strength of the financial Framework. But challenges exist in improving financial access, insuring financial support for small and medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), and further enhancing sound regulatory oversight.

Grappling with India's National Biometric- based Payment System

The uneven road to scaling ordinal financial services through the Aadhaar assisted payment system.

By Rahul Ranjan Sinha and Gaurav chakrabarty Grameen Foundation India, may 2018.

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India's Aadhaar enabled payment system (AEPS) stands the world's first national biometric-grounded payments system. In the two years meanwhile its launch, AEPS by way of offered both advantage and challenges as it pursues to expand financial inclusion. Grameen Foundation India takes experienced these directly by way of we work to scale numeral financial services and fiscal education.

How does AEPS Work?

AEPS was considered to allow individuals to manner financial transactions across any contributing Bank, using just three inputs:

- A number recognising the bank;
- The customer's own national credentials number, assigned using biometric data such as thumbprints for identification; and
- The customer's thumb print, which provides user verification at the time of transaction.

Transaction can take place at a Bank recorded with the system, or at sales machine setup over banks "business correspondents" such as microfinance institutions. This carry accessibility and cost savings to rural clients who live far as of a bank branch.

Grameen Foundation India's Experience with AEPS

In a project financed by CITI Foundation, we combined in AEPS to help large financial inclusion for Meagre and low income females in the state of Uttar Pradesh. With our companion Sonata finance, a principal Indian MFI and oxygen a primary payment solution provider, the project extended out to women complete 150 Sonata branches, where trained staff can assist clients by the digitally- based POS machines.

From March 2017 to November 2017, clients prepared more than 32000 transactions worth US\$110,448 (INR 74 million) At Sonata branches. They made expenditures on individual or collection loans from Sonata, pledges and withdrawals. More than 58,600 females clients were qualified on the AEPS platform, besides 15760 made transactions.

An impact study of the project imprinted out some of the key rewards and challenges faced with AEPS stage

Key Advantages for Women Client

- High trust- Most of the low income women clients well illiterate: - 76% of clients had completed no more than primary education. When visiting a bank on their own, this women wear dependent on strangers for filling deposits or withdrawal forms the AEPS platform meant there where fewer forms to fill, and women assisted by the trusted local branch staff. This became a big

incentives for women to adopt digital Financial Services.

- Convenience and interoperability: -Clients appreciated being able to make multiple transactions for different accounts at different banks under single roof, saving time and travel expenses. Previously, clients active at a distant location oftencovered as a group to do their finance, for reasons of both care and friendship.
- Ease of transaction: -Clients didn't have to provide any document apart from the Adhar number previously they needed bank passbooks and related documents, and just signing the documents could be intimidating.
- No transaction fees: -Unlike mobile wallets AEPS does not charge any service fee to the client. Mobile wallet fees could be as high as 1.5 % to 2% of the transaction amount.

Key Challenges for Clients

- **High transaction failure rate:** -About 56% of the total transactions conducted during the project period failed, compared to 60% failure rate for AEPS Nationally. This is astronomical by any standards. About 20% of the failed transactions were due to user issues, including incorrect Aadhaar number and insufficient bank balance. About 45% were due to technical glitches, including poor internet connectivity.
- **Biometric mismatch:** -Around 35% of the disastrous transactions were due to biometric disparity. Most women clients were engaged in job requiring rigorous manual labour which resulted in eroded fingerprints that led to failed fingerprint recognition. This results in the exclusion of a large section of society, which is unable to reap the immense benefit of this platform.
- **Failed transaction producing balance deductions:** In many circumstances, transaction miscarried to complete, but compensation amounts were still withheld from clients' explanations. Furthermore, it took coarsely a month for the volume to be reposted. This is a major fence, especially for low-income households whose small amounts had little margin for error.

Clearly, All through benefits to the system where strong, operational challenges present several limitations to the AEPS system. Due to the regular let-down of transactions, many customers expressed feeling disheartened from using the policy.

For AEPS to distribute fully on its promise of increasing financial inclusion in India, these involvements. To the need for several crucial changes AEPS must reduce the number of failed transactions, and expedite the redress of failed transaction. To do so, three core issues must be addressed:

- Finding a practical substitute to fingerprint authentication;
- Continuing to strengthen the internet infrastructure in rural areas ;and
- Complementary efforts to strengthen the digital and financial literacy of low income women such that they enter the banking environment confident and well prepared.

Being Smart about Mobile Money

Leveraging client fortification principles for Savings clusters in Burkina Faso

By Bobbi Grey and Christian Loupeda, Grameen Foundation, April 2018

Bobbi grey is research director and leads research, evaluation and social performance management initiatives of Grameen Foundation. Christian Loupeda is senior director, financial inclusion and globally leads Grameen Foundation's financial services initiatives which include savings groups, formal financial services and digital Financial Services.

Digital finance evokes images of topping to cell phone and instantaneous transactions. Loans, transfers, and payment we may think of the well-known M-paisa, the mobile phone based money

transfer and microfinance service launched by or Vodafone in Kenya and Tanzania, are many similar services across the globe. While sub-Saharan Africa might lead the world in itinerant money accounts 21% of immature have 1 some country static lack the infrastructure and skill with mobile money. In addition in these countries, superior guests needed to protect new low income Users who are likely using ordinal financial services for the first time.

In 2014 in Burkina Faso, for example 15% of men had a formal financial account and 12% of women did. Compared to the average of sub-Saharan Africa, only 3.1% of men and women in Burkina Faso had a mobile money account and this was even less among the poorest and this rural areas. However, it was assessed that almost 25% of females in Burkina were saving with some sort of casual savings group (SG), likely secretarial for the majority of financial communications among females as this blog stayed going to press, the greatest recent set of world-wide index numbers were efficient, suggesting enhancements in this number crossways the board.

Given the popularity of savings groups for Burkinabe women we wanted to know: could they be brought into the formal financial system with savings account access via a mobile phone platform? So we set out to test this idea.

Among 2014 and 2016, Grameen Foundation, by support from UNCDF micro LED thrown the bridge to financial insertion project in Burkina Faso towards test whether official financial service provides (FSPs) might form their own reserves Groups for Poor countryside women, and link those clusters to formal savings excuse via a mobile phone platform. In alliance with two Burkinabe FSPs, Le re se au des caisses popularities du Burkina Faso (RCPB) and la societe de financement de la petite enterprise (SOFIPE), we began emerging a large network of self-managed reserves groups and linking them to a specific groups savings accounts through mobile technology.

While both RCPB and SOFIPE on condition that financial education to the cluster members and recycled mobile phone technology to link sets to formal savings account, this stood where the similarity of their mock-ups ended.

SOFIPE used third party airtel money (now orange) platform for the mobile linkage of SGS for formal group savings accounts. Were as RCPB use their own in house application intercaisses (or inter-credit union) which in the past primarily facilitated money transfers for clients within RCPB's credit union system both approaches approved with thema set of threat to the savings clutch members given the freshness of mobile money, in toting to other risks related to every approach, such as the starring role of third party actors. Client creation, therefore, was essential and necessary to the project.

With supplementary support from the accountable microfinance fund (RMF), Grameen foundation established a case study to document how the project control the seven existing client fabrication principles from the insolent campaign not only to monitor product development then also to assess any threats to client production. The project documented seven main obstacles to client protection:

- Client understanding;
- Affordability of the product;
- Network down time;
- Fraud;
- Absence of recourse;
- Insufficient agent liquidity;
- Cultural barriers;

Anyone of these seven risks could result in a bad experience for the savings group members, and lots of trust and confidence in RCPB and SOFIPE specifically, and in mobile money, generally. To discourse these barriers RCPB, SOFIPE, grameen foundation then smart companion mentors met

prior to the product expansion to create work strategies that would recognise and address risks to client defence.

While this specifics of how each FSP addressed this barriers are documented in the report, the experience demonstrate how the clients protection principles were useful not only for assessing how well financial services protect clients, but also and maybe more importantly for designing responsible digital financial services (DFS) for vulnerable population.

Addressing the risk related to client empathetic priority for the project, has most stashes group members were Untaught, poor, lacked mobile phone knowledge, and many had no previous experience employed with all formal FSP. Meanwhile mobile phone practice was low, agent's mobile phone happened used both to classification the SG members as well as to help them in making the portable money transactions. Ensuring adequate liquidity required a abundant deal of coordination among the SGS and the agents, not to indicate the challenge of identifying the right means to support savings groups.

The bridge to fiscal inclusion project mandatory much more and holding then almost certainly across in places like Kenya there the DFS ecosystem is innovative and even the remotest of villages use mobile Money.

Burkina Faso is in conversion, and no doubt resolve one day be as active a DFS market as Kenya. aimed now, as Burkina Faso's anticipate a robust DFS infrastructure that capacities to facilitate greater fiscal inclusion, cautious and patient DFS projects and funds are needed to help build trust and willingness for the most excluded. This includes plans that strengthen the monetary and digital literacy of operator as well as those that maintenance FSPs to fully incorporated user risk mitigation strategies into their creation design and discovery mechanism.

Keeping client protection at the centre of this efforts not only makes good business since for FSPs but also made determine how well and hoe quickly people become active users of the DFS as the market grows.

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